

Article

Downsizing Sustainable Aviation Fuel Production with Additive Manufacturing – An Experimental Study on a 3D printed Reactor for Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis: Supplementary Information

David Metzger ^{1,*}, Christoph Klahn ² and Roland Dittmeyer ¹

¹ Institute for Micro Process Engineering (IMVT), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Herrmann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany

² Institute of Mechanics and Mechanical Process Engineering (MVM), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), B. 30.70, Strasse am Forum 8, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

* Correspondence: david.metzger@kit.edu, +49 721 608 23047

Citation: To be added by editorial staff during production.

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Revised: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

Copyright: © 2023 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Materials

The materials employed in the experiments are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Materials.

Name	Company	Product
Male threaded connectors	Swagelok	SS-6M0-1-2RS, SS-12M0-1-8RS
Metal gasket	Swagelok	304L-2-RSNB-2, 304L-8-RSNB-2
Sinter metal	GKN	SIKA-R 100 AX, $t = 2$ mm
Graphite sealing	Frenzelit	Novaphit VS, $t = 2$ mm
Thermocouples	Conatex	Type K (NiCr-Ni) OD 0.5 mm; 1 mm
Heating cartridges	Kleinesdar	OD ¼", 100 W @ 230 VAC
Thermal conductivity paste	IBF Chemotechnik Elektronik GmbH	Ferotherm 4
Mass flow controllers (MFC)	Brooks	$\dot{V}_{N_2} = 30 \frac{\text{mL}_N}{\text{min}}$; $\dot{V}_{H_2} = 600 \frac{\text{mL}_N}{\text{min}}$; $\dot{V}_{CO} = 300 \frac{\text{mL}_N}{\text{min}}$
Oil thermostat	Lauda	Proline P12C
Thermal oil	Fragol	Fragoltherm 660
Insulation material	Isover	U Protect Pipe Sect- Alu2
Preprocessing software	DMG MORI	RDesigner (version 1.23.01, Revision 2017)
Printer operating Software	DMG MORI	ROperator (version 1.0.2.376, Revision 943 (2018))
Printer	DMG MORI	Realizer SLM 125
Purge gas	Air Liquide	Argon 5.0
Metal powder	Carpenter Additive	CT PowderRange 316LF
NC mill	Deckel	FP5
Laboratory scale	Kern und Sohn	ABS-N ABJ-NM

AM Scan Strategy

Table 2 contains details on the additive manufacturing strategy employed in this work.

Table 2: Scan strategy: order and details of features.

Detail	Value	Unit
0. General		
Heating	True	
h_{layer}	0.05	mm
Heat function	True	
1. Hatch		
Exposure time ET	10	μs
Point distance PD	10	μm
Scan velocity SV	1	m s^{-1}
Power P	110	W
Lens position LP	0.6	mm
To 1. Advanced hatch definition		
Initial offset	0.12	mm
Hatch distance	0.08	mm
Rotation	93	$^{\circ}$
Scan direction	Alternating	
Multiply method	Random	

Shifted Patch size	True	
	8 x 5	mm
2.+3. Fill line		
<i>ET</i>	50	μs
<i>PD</i>	10	μm
<i>SV</i>	0.2	m s ⁻¹
<i>P</i>	110	W
<i>LP</i>	0.2	mm
Base offset	0.08	mm
4.+5. Inner contours, 6.+7. outer contours		
<i>ET</i>	50	μs
<i>PD</i>	10	μm
<i>SV</i>	0.2	m s ⁻¹
<i>P</i>	110	W
<i>LP</i>	0.2	mm

20

AM Porous Region

21

Preliminary tests revealed for the hydrodynamic behavior of the frit the following values according to ISO 4022 [1]: $\Psi_V = 0.5 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$ and $\Psi_I = 0.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}$. This relates to a pressure drop at $T = 234 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $p = 20 \text{ bar}$ and $F = 30 \text{ L}_N \text{ h}^{-1}$ of $\Delta p = 1000 \text{ Pa}$. The pressure drop of a packed bed with $d_p = 100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $\varepsilon = 0.5$ is negligible.

22

23

24

25

Test Rig

26

In Figure 1 the process flow diagram of the test rig is shown.

27

Figure 1: Process flow diagram of test rig.

28

In Figure 2 the test rig and reactor are shown. The connection of the oil thermostat to the reactor is clearly visible.

29

30

Figure 2: Reactor in test rig. Left: Reactor partially insulated. Right: Reactor (very top) insulated, oil lines and thermostat (bottom) connected.

31

GC Results and Product Distribution

32

Calculating molar flows from online GC: $\dot{N}_{i,out} = y_{i,out} \cdot \frac{\dot{N}_{N_2}}{y_{N_2,out}}$. Mass fraction of component with i C atoms ω_i [2,3] correlates with signal area in oil and wax GC [2,4]:

33

34

$$\omega_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum_{i=a}^b A_i}$$

35

$$\omega_i = i \cdot (1 - \alpha)^2 \cdot \alpha^{i-1}$$

36

$$\alpha = \frac{i-1}{i} \cdot \frac{\omega_i}{\omega_{i-1}}$$

37

Molar fraction of component with i C atoms x_i [5,6]: $x_i = (1 - \alpha) \cdot \alpha^{i-1}$. Molar mass of alkane with i C atoms: $\tilde{M}_i = i \cdot \tilde{M}_C + (2 \cdot i + 2) \cdot \tilde{M}_H$; $\frac{\tilde{M}_i}{i \cdot \tilde{M}_C} = \dots$ for $i \rightarrow \infty = 1.17$

38

39

40

Conversion over TOS

41

The CO conversion over time on stream is depicted in Figure 3.

42

Figure 3: CO conversion over time on stream. Between setpoints 12 and 13 was an extended GC shutdown. 43
44

Fit of Conversion to Temperature and Space Velocity 45

The experimental data was fitted with the following fit: $\hat{X}_{CO,fit} = a + b \cdot \hat{SV}_{mod} + c \cdot$ 46
 \hat{T} with $\hat{X}_{CO,fit} = \frac{X_{CO}^{max} - X_{CO}}{X_{CO}^{max} - X_{CO}^{min}}$ and $\hat{T} = \frac{T^{max} - T}{T^{max} - T^{min}}$ and $\hat{SV}_{mod} = \frac{SV_{mod}^{max} - SV_{mod}}{SV_{mod}^{max} - SV_{mod}^{min}}$ and $X_{CO}^{max} = 90$ 47
and $X_{CO}^{min} = 10$ and $T^{max} = 240$ and $T^{min} = 185$ and $SV_{mod}^{max} = 10$ and $SV_{mod}^{min} = 1$ and 48
 $a = 0.2438$ and $b = -0.7168$ and $c = 1.2733$. The quality of the fit is depicted in 49
Figure 4. 50

Figure 4: Quality of the fit. Left: Residuals over fitted parameter. Right: Parity plot of experimental and fitted value.

Comparison with Literature

The space time yield can be calculated from gas flow and CO conversion based on equations Eq. 1 and 2. Assumptions Eqs. 3-8 are derived from an ideal Anderson-Schulz-Flory (ASF) product distribution for a chain growth probability of $\alpha = 0.85$. The values of α and S_{C5+} obtained in experiments confirm these assumptions.

$$STY_{calc} = X_{CO} \cdot SV_{mod} \cdot \rho_{cat} \cdot y_{CO,in} \cdot S_{C5+} \cdot M_{C5+} \cdot \frac{1}{n_{C5+} \cdot V_N} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$STY_{calc}/\text{kg}_{C5+} \text{ m}_{rct}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1} = X_{CO}/\% \cdot SV_{mod}/L_N \text{ g}_{cat}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \cdot 1.226 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\text{With: } \rho_{cat} = 750 \frac{\text{kg}_{cat}}{\text{m}_{rct}^3}, y_{CO,in} = 0.323; S_{C5+} \approx 0.8;$$

$$M_{C5+} = 151 \frac{\text{g}_{C5+}}{\text{mol}}; n_{C5+} = 10.65; V_N = 22.41 \frac{L_N}{\text{mol}} \quad \text{Eqs. 3-8}$$

The calculated space time yield is depicted in the area generated by modified space velocity and the CO conversion in Figure 5. The STY increases to the top right of the corner. The CO conversion that can be achieved at a certain SV_{mod} and T depends on the catalyst. The activity of the catalysts used are in increasing order: work of Almeida et al. [7], this work, work of Myrstad et al. [8].

Figure 5: Experimental CO conversion in the plane generated by modified space velocity and temperature with STY in $\text{kg}_{\text{C5+}} \text{m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$ next to the respective data point. Literature values from Almeida et al. and Myrstad et al. [7,8].

In the following Table 3 we make estimations on a scaled-up AM reactor and compare it to industrial FTS reactors. For these reactors we found data on the productivity per reactor mass MP in barrel per day (bpd).

Table 3: Reactor in this work.

Calculation	Comment/Source
$P = 3.4 \text{ g}_{\text{C5+}} \text{h}^{-1}$ $m_{\text{cat}} = 3.4 \text{ g}_{\text{cat}}$ $STY_{\text{mod}} = 1 \text{ g}_{\text{C5+}} \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ $STY = 0.75 \text{ g}_{\text{C5+}} \text{cm}_{\text{cat}}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$	With $\rho_{\text{cat}} = 0.75 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ Assuming infinitely extended planar slits, a repetition unit is made up of a reaction slit containing 10 % internal structures, two walls and a cooling slit containing 10 % internal structures. All slits are 1 mm deep and wall thickness is 1 mm. Hence, approx. 2.2 cm^3 metal per cm^3 catalyst are needed. With $\rho_{\text{metal}} = 8 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ approx. 17.6 g metal per cm^3 catalyst are needed.
$MP = 0.0426 \text{ g}_{\text{C5+}} \text{g}_{\text{metal}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} =$ $42.6 \text{ kg}_{\text{C5+}} \text{t}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ $1 \text{ bl} = 159 \text{ L}$ $1 \text{ bl} = 127.2 \text{ kg}$ $1 \text{ bpd (bl per day)} = 5.3 \text{ kg h}^{-1}$ $MP = 8.038 \text{ bpd t}^{-1}$	With $\rho = 0.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ With 24 h d ⁻¹

Table 4: Shell Pearl GTL.

72

Calculation	Comment/Source
140,000 bpd	[9]
$m_{\text{reactor}} = 1200 \text{ t}$ (24 in total)	[10]
$MP = 5833 \text{ bpd per reactor} = 4.861 \text{ bpd t}^{-1}$	

73

Table 5: Sasol Oryx GTL.

74

Calculation	Comment/Source
33,000 bpd	[11]
$m_{\text{reactor}} = 2000 \text{ t}$ (2 in total)	[12]
$MP = 16500 \text{ bpd per reactor} = 8.25 \text{ bpd t}^{-1}$	

75

A scaled-up version of the AM reactor can produce as much FTS product as an industrial-scale reactor with the equal reactor mass. Compact reactors that are manufactured via complex multi-step manufacturing routes, e.g. diffusion bonding, are researched since ca. 20 years. They are reported to have productivities per reactor mass of $MP = 13$ and 16.5 bpd t^{-1} [13].

76

77

78

79

80

81

Scale-Up

82

An eight-fold scale-up of the reactor is shown in Figure 6. It would be possible to install about $m_{\text{cat}} = 30 \text{ g}$.

83

84

85

Figure 6: Computer-aided design image of reactor concept for $m_{\text{cat}} = 30 \text{ g}$.

86

87

88

Evaluation of heat and mass transfer

We evaluated the following criteria to decide whether heat and mass transfer were limiting the chemical reaction. The axial dispersion of mass is insignificant as long as Eq. 9 is fulfilled [14]. The left-hand side equals 380.

$$\frac{l_{\text{cat}}}{d_p} > \frac{8}{Bo_i} \cdot n_i \cdot \ln\left(\frac{1}{1-X_i}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$\frac{1}{Bo_i} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{bed}} \cdot D_{i,m}}{\tau_{\text{bed}} \cdot d_p \cdot u_0} + 0.5$$

$i = \text{H}_2, \text{CO}$

The internal mass transfer limitation is insignificant if Eq. 10 is fulfilled [15]. Ψ_{WP} is called Weisz-Prater criterion.

$$\Psi_{\text{WP}} = \frac{\left(\frac{d_p}{6}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{n_i + 1}{2} \cdot r_i^{\text{V}}}{(1 - \varepsilon_{\text{bed}}) \cdot D_{i,\text{eff}} \cdot c_{i,g}} < 0.15 \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$i = \text{H}_2, \text{CO}$

External mass transfer limitation is insignificant as long as Eq. 11 is fulfilled [15].

$$\frac{d_p^2 \cdot r_i^{\text{V}}}{12 \cdot (1 - \varepsilon_{\text{bed}}) \cdot D_{i,m} \cdot c_{i,g}} < 1 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$i = \text{H}_2, \text{CO}$

The internal heat transfer limitation is insignificant if Eq. 12 is fulfilled [16].

$$\frac{-\Delta H_R \cdot \left(\frac{d_p}{2}\right)^2 \cdot r_{\text{CO}}^{\text{V}} \cdot \frac{E_A}{\tilde{R} \cdot T_s}}{(1 - \varepsilon_{\text{bed}}) \cdot \lambda_{\text{bed}} \cdot T_s} < 1 \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

External heat transfer limitation is insignificant as long as Eq. 13 is fulfilled [16].

$$\frac{-\Delta H_R \cdot \frac{d_p}{2} \cdot r_{\text{CO}}^{\text{V}} \cdot \frac{E_A}{\tilde{R} \cdot T_s}}{(1 - \varepsilon_{\text{bed}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{gas}} \cdot T_s} < 0.05 \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

Additional values were calculated according to eqs.

$$c_i = \frac{y_i \cdot p}{\tilde{R} \cdot T} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$\dot{N}_{\text{total}} = \frac{F_{\text{total}}}{V_{\text{N}}} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

$$\dot{N}_{\text{CO,conv}} = \dot{N}_{\text{total}} \cdot y_{\text{CO,in}} \cdot X_{\text{CO}} \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

$$r_{\text{CO}}^{\text{V}} = \frac{\dot{N}_{\text{CO,conv}}}{V_{\text{cat}}}; r_{\text{H}_2}^{\text{V}} = 2 \cdot r_{\text{CO}}^{\text{V}} \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

$$F_{\text{total}}^{\text{actual}} = F_{\text{total}} \cdot \frac{p_{\text{N}}}{p} \cdot \frac{T}{T_{\text{N}}} \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

$$u_0 = \frac{F_{\text{total}}^{\text{actual}}}{A_{\text{cross}}} \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

89

90

91

92

93

94

95

96

97

98

99

100

101

102

103

104

105

106

107

108

109

110

111

112

113

114

115

116

Table 6: Additional parameters required for criteria calculation.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Source
Bed length	l_{cat}	0.055 m	
Bed porosity	ε_{bed}	0.5	
Mixture diffusivity	$D_{\text{H}_2,\text{m}}$	$6.86 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
Mixture diffusivity	$D_{\text{CO},\text{m}}$	$6.05 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
Bed tortuosity	τ_{bed}	2	
Particle diameter	d_p	0.00015 m	
Reaction order	n_{H_2}	0.5	
Reaction order	n_{CO}	1	
Effective pore diffusivity	$D_{\text{H}_2,\text{eff}}, D_{\text{CO},\text{eff}}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
Reaction enthalpy	ΔH_{R}	$-160000 \text{ J molCO}^{-1}$	
Bed thermal conductivity	λ_{bed}	$1 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$	
Activation energy	E_A	100 J molCO^{-1}	
Inlet molar fraction	y_{H_2}	0.646	
Inlet molar fraction	y_{CO}	0.323	
Bed-gas heat transfer coefficient	α_{gas}	$5267 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$	With $\lambda_{\text{gas}} = 0.16 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $Nu_{\text{min}} = 5$
Molar volume	V_{N}	$22.41 \text{ LN mol}^{-1}$	
Cross-sectional area	A_{cross}	80 mm^2	

117

Table 7: Results of criteria indicate, there is no limitation by heat and mass transfer.

N.	$T / ^\circ\text{C}$	SV_{mod} / L_N $\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	F_{total} / L_N h^{-1}	$X_{\text{CO}} / \%$	$X_{\text{H}_2} / \%$	$c_{\text{H}_2} / \text{mol m}^{-3}$	$c_{\text{CO}} / \text{mol m}^{-3}$	$r_{\text{H}_2^V} / \text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$	$r_{\text{CO}^V} / \text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$	$u_0 / \text{mm s}^{-1}$	Eq. 9 H2	Eq. 9 CO	Eq. 10 H2	Eq. 10 CO	Eq. 11 H2	Eq. 11 CO	Eq. 12	Eq. 13
1	200	3.59	12.0	39.3	36.7	329	164	8.57	4.28	3.60	59	114	0.00	0.01	1.43E-06	1.62E-06	4.14E-04	1.05E-03
2	209	3.59	12.0	52.6	51.5	322	161	11.45	5.73	3.67	92	167	0.01	0.01	1.94E-06	2.20E-06	5.34E-04	1.35E-03
3	219	3.59	12.0	70.9	72.4	316	158	15.46	7.73	3.75	160	271	0.01	0.01	2.68E-06	3.03E-06	6.91E-04	1.75E-03
4	219	5.38	17.9	56.0	55.8	316	158	18.30	9.15	5.61	68	121	0.01	0.01	3.17E-06	3.59E-06	8.18E-04	2.07E-03
5	229	5.38	17.9	79.0	80.6	310	155	25.80	12.90	5.73	134	226	0.02	0.02	4.56E-06	5.17E-06	1.11E-03	2.81E-03
6	209	5.38	17.9	43.3	41.2	322	161	14.15	7.08	5.50	45	86	0.01	0.01	2.40E-06	2.72E-06	6.59E-04	1.67E-03
7	200	5.38	17.9	27.8	26.5	329	164	9.07	4.54	5.40	27	50	0.01	0.01	1.51E-06	1.71E-06	4.39E-04	1.11E-03
8	209	1.85	6.2	65.1	67.7	322	161	7.31	3.66	1.89	276	453 ¹	0.00	0.01	1.24E-06	1.41E-06	3.41E-04	8.62E-04
9	200	1.85	6.2	53.0	53.5	329	164	5.96	2.98	1.86	190	331	0.00	0.00	9.91E-07	1.12E-06	2.88E-04	7.30E-04
10	190	1.85	6.2	31.4	31.2	336	168	3.52	1.76	1.82	95	169	0.00	0.00	5.74E-07	6.51E-07	1.78E-04	4.50E-04
11	209	9.00	30.0	16.9	16.6	322	161	9.23	4.62	9.20	9	17	0.01	0.01	1.57E-06	1.78E-06	4.30E-04	1.09E-03
12	229	9.00	30.0	48.5	50.5	310	155	26.51	13.25	9.58	35	59	0.02	0.02	4.68E-06	5.31E-06	1.14E-03	2.88E-03
13	219	9.00	30.0	38.5	38.4	316	158	21.03	10.52	9.39	25	44	0.01	0.02	3.64E-06	4.13E-06	9.41E-04	2.38E-03
14	234	9.00	30.0	69.2	71.0	307	153	37.82	18.91	9.68	61	103	0.02	0.03	6.75E-06	7.65E-06	1.59E-03	4.03E-03
1R	200	3.59	12.0	42.3	41.2	329	164	9.22	4.61	3.60	68	125	0.01	0.01	1.53E-06	1.74E-06	4.46E-04	1.13E-03

¹Only incident, where criterion is not fulfilled.

References

1. DIN e.V. *Durchlässige Sintermetallwerkstoffe: Bestimmung der Flüssigkeitsdurchlässigkeit*, 2018, 77.160 (4022). 129
2. Kirsch, H. *Dezentrale Synthese strombasierter flüssiger Kraftstoffe über die Fischer-Tropsch Route*; Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Karlsruhe, 2020. 130
131
3. Flory, P.J. Molecular Size Distribution in Linear Condensation Polymers. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1936**, *58*, 1877–1885. 132
133
4. Kaiser, R.E. *Gas-Chromatographie*, 1973. 134
5. Brübach, L.T. *Katalytische Hydrierende Spaltung von Fischer-Tropsch Produkten im Technikumsmaßstab*. Masterarbeit; Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, 2018. 135
136
6. Pabst, K.; González, M.I.; Kraushaar-Czarnetzki, B.; Schaub, G. Combination of Fischer–Tropsch Synthesis and Hydroprocessing in a Single-Stage Reactor. Part I. Mathematical Modeling of the Reaction Kinetics. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2013**, *52*, 8978–8987, doi:10.1021/ie303047a. 137
138
139
7. Almeida, L.C.; Echave, F.J.; Sanz, O.; Centeno, M.A.; Arzamendi, G.; Gandía, L.M.; Sousa-Aguiar, E.F.; Odriozola, J.A.; Montes, M. Fischer–Tropsch synthesis in microchannels. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2011**, *167*, 536–544, doi:10.1016/j.cej.2010.09.091. 140
141
142
8. Myrstad, R.; Eri, S.; Pfeifer, P.; Rytter, E.; Holmen, A. Fischer–Tropsch synthesis in a microstructured reactor. *Catalysis Today* **2009**, *147*, S301–S304, doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2009.07.011. 143
144
9. Shell. Pearl GTL Overview. Available online: <https://www.shell.com/about-us/major-projects/pearl-gtl/pearl-gtl-an-overview.html> (accessed on 3 July 2023). 145
146
10. MAN Energy Solutions. Shell Pearl GTL – Gas-to-liquid reactor in Qatar for Shell. Available online: <https://www.man-es.com/process-industry/products/chemical-reactors/water--air--oil-operated-reactors> (accessed on 3 July 2023). 147
148
149
11. Hydrocarbons Technology. Oryx. Available online: <https://www.hydrocarbons-technology.com/projects/oryx/> (accessed on 3 July 2023). 150
151
12. Technip. *Oryx GTL*, 2011. Available online: <https://docplayer.net/45263490-Our-projects-oryx-gtl.html> (accessed on 25 August 2023). 152
153
13. Selinsek, M. *Compact Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis in Gas-to-Liquid Applications*. Litvinov, Prague, May 23, 2019. 154
14. Berger, R. *EUROKIN spreadsheet on requirements for measurement of intrinsic kinetics in the gas-solid fixed-bed reactor*, 2010. Available online: https://eurokin.org/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2019/08/EUROKIN_fixed-bed_html_guide.pdf (accessed on 15 September 2023). 155
156
157
15. Jess, A.; Wasserscheid, P. *Chemical technology: An integral textbook*; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, 2013, ISBN 978-3-527-30446-2. 158
159
16. Pfeifer, P. Application of catalysts to metal microreactor systems. In *Chemical Kinetics*; Patel, V., Ed.; InTech Europe: Rijeka, 2012; pp 325–345, ISBN 978-953-51-0132-1. 160
161
162

List of Symbols

Latin symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
A	Area	mm ²
F	Volumetric flow rate	L _N h ⁻¹
\tilde{M}	Molar mass	d
MP	Productivity per reactor mass	bpd t ⁻¹
m	Mass	kg
\dot{N}	Molar flow	mol s ⁻¹
nc	Number of carbon atoms	-
P	Productivity of C5+	kg s ⁻¹ ; g h ⁻¹
p	Pressure	bar
S	Selectivity	-
STY	Space time yield	kg m ⁻³ h ⁻¹
SV	Space velocity at normal conditions	L _N m ⁻³ h ⁻¹
T	Temperature	K
TOS	Time on stream	h
V	Volume	mm ³
t	Thickness, dimension	mm
X	Conversion	-
y	Molar fraction	-

165

Greek symbols

166

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
α	Chain growth probability	-
Δ	Difference	-
ε	Porosity	-
Ψ	Permeability coefficients	m ⁻¹ , m ⁻²
ω	Weight fraction	-

Indices

167

Symbol	Meaning
cat	Catalyst
I	Inertia permeability coefficient
mod	Modified, in this work: related to catalyst mass
N	Normal conditions (p=1.01325 bara, T=273.15 K)
p	Particle, pin
V	Permeability coefficient of flow

168